

Analysis of Personal Protective Equipment (Ppe) Inventory Control Using ABC Analysis and Economic Order Quantity (EOQ)

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ABSTRACT

PT. Mitra Ciruas Food (MCF) is a company operating in the catering services sector. Apart from that, PT. MCF also provides catering services for certain events. Personal protective equipment is very important for catering companies, because it ensures the hygiene of the product produced, namely food or drink. The aim of this research is to classify personal protective equipment using the ABC method and find out when is the right time to order personal protective equipment so that there is no shortage of supplies using the EOQ method. This research includes collecting data on the use of personal protective equipment in 2022. Data analysis was carried out using Microsoft Excel. Grouping of personal protective equipment based on the ABC method by looking at the highest value. The results of the analysis using the ABC method showed that 2 types of personal protective equipment items were included in classification A, namely latex gloves and hair nets with a percentage of 57,935% of the total inventory of personal protective equipment with a total value of Rp1,562,500.00. Based on the results of calculations using the Economic Order Quantity method, the number of economic orders for group A, namely latex gloves, is 198 pcs for one order, while the frequency of ordering latex gloves is 4 times and reordering when the supply of latex gloves has reached 24 items. . And to *hair netis* 73 pcs for one order while the order frequency *hair netis* 3 times as well as reordering when stock is available *hair netis* has reached 8 items.

INTRODUCTION

Business development at this time has grown rapidly, especially business in the food sector. As business develops, competition between companies becomes increasingly fierce. Therefore, personal protective equipment is very necessary in companies, especially those operating in the food sector. To maintain the quality and cleanliness of the products produced. To maintain the availability of personal protective equipment, PT Mitra Ciruas Food's planning and procurement of personal protective equipment must be managed well. In general, PT Mitra Ciruas Food carries out inventory planning and control based on previous experience, so that sometimes PT Mitra Ciruas Food experiences inventory shortages. This is because the amount needed always changes depending on usage.

The supply of personal protective equipment is an important factor to support the smooth running of activities carried out in a company. Therefore, companies need to pay attention to the supply of personal protective equipment so that the amount of personal protective equipment is always sufficient, and they do not experience shortages or running out of stock because it can hinder activities in the company. Excess personal protective equipment is also not good because it can result in increased company costs.

To know the need for supplies of personal protective equipment for a company, management is needed. Inventory management is an important thing to pay attention to in a company, because inventory management concerns how the company can control materials in carrying out activities for receiving, storing, maintaining and distributing materials from the results of procurement and storage of inventory management

Identification of problems

1. There is always a shortage of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE).
2. There is no priority grouping of PPE and it is not yet known which PPE consumes the highest funds.
3. It is not yet known how much Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) must be ordered and when it will be ordered.

Formulation of the problem

1. Based on ABC analysis, what are the results of the classification of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) and which Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) consumes the highest funds?
2. How much Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) needs to be reordered?

Research purposes

1. Find out which Personal Protective Equipment groupings and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) groups consume the highest funds at PT. MCF.

Analyze and find out how much Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) needs to be ordered and when it needs to be reordered.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Analysis and Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) is a method used in supply chain management to identify the optimal order quantity that will result in the most economical total ordering and holding costs. The method aims to find a balance between the costs of ordering goods in large quantities (having lower ordering costs) and the costs of holding goods (having lower holding costs). Key points of EOQ involve calculating the optimal order quantity by considering ordering and holding costs. Some main elements in the EOQ concept include:

1. Ordering Cost: Costs associated with the process of ordering goods, including administrative costs, order processing, and others.
2. Holding Cost: Costs incurred due to storing goods, such as warehouse rental costs, insurance, and depreciation costs for stored goods.
3. Demand Rate:** The quantity of goods needed during a specific period.

By considering these elements, EOQ determines the optimal quantity of goods to be ordered in each order cycle. This optimal quantity is designed to minimize total ordering and holding costs. The EOQ approach helps organizations efficiently manage inventory and avoid unnecessary costs.

The mathematical formulation of EOQ can be done using the following formula:

$$EOQ = \sqrt{\frac{2DS}{H}}$$

where:

D is the demand rate (in units per period),
S is the ordering cost per order, and
H is the holding cost per unit per period.

EOQ provides valuable guidance to companies in determining the optimal order size, helping maintain a balance between ordering costs and holding costs, and optimizing supply chain efficiency.

METHODOLOGY

Figure 1.1 Research Flow Chart

Data on the Use of Personal Protective Equipment

No	Name of PPE	Total Usage (1 year)	Price of PPE / PCS (Rp)
1	Latex Gloves	814	1,250.00
2	Hairnets	218	2,500.00
3	Plastic Apron	815	600.00
4	Face mask	841	500.00
5	Cloth Aprons	5	30,000.00
6	Plastic gloves	752	100.00

Data processing

Data processing was carried out by data analysis using the ABC and EOQ methods. The following steps are taken:

Analysis Using the ABC Method

The ABC method analysis was carried out through 3 stages of the type of personal protective equipment with the highest use. The data used in this method is personal protective equipment for the period of use in 2022 and is sorted from the highest amount of expenditure to the lowest, then grouped into 3:

1. Group A with a cumulative percentage of 0-70%
2. Group B with a cumulative percentage of 71-90%
3. Group C with a cumulative percentage of 91-100%

Calculation of Personal Protective Equipment Use Based on Expenditure

No	Name of PPE	Total Usage (1 Year)	Price of PPE / PCS (Rp)	Total Expenditures (Rp)
1	Latex Gloves	814	1,250.00	1,017,500.00
2	Hairnets	218	2,500.00	545,000.00
3	Plastic Apron	815	600.00	489,000.00
4	Face mask	841	500.00	420,000.00
5	Cloth Aprons	5	30,000.00	150,000.00
6	Plastic gloves	752	100.00	75,500.00

Calculation of Expenditure Percentage and Cumulative Percentage

No	Name of PPE	Total Expenditures (Rp)	% Expenditure	Cumulative %
1	Latex Gloves	1,017,500.00	37,727	37,727
2	Hairnets	545,000.00	20,208	57,935
3	Plastic Apron	489,000.00	18,131	76,066
4	Face mask	420,000.00	15,573	91,639
5	Cloth Aprons	150,000.00	5,562	97,201
6	Plastic gloves	75,500.00	2,799	100,000
Total		2,697,000.00	100	

ABC Grouping based on Cumulative Value

No	Name of PPE	Cumulative %	Class
1	Latex Gloves	37,727	A
2	Hairnets	57,935	A
3	Plastic Apron	76,066	B
4	Face mask	91,639	C
5	Cloth Aprons	97.201	C
6	Plastic gloves	100	C

Grouping Personal Protective Equipment Based on Highest Value

PPE Group	Amount of PPE	% Number of PPE Types	Mark (Rp)
A	1032	57,935	1,562,500.00
B	1039	18,131	489,000.00
C	757	23,934	645,500.00
Total	2828	100	2,697,000.00

EOQ Calculation Analysis

To determine EOQ, calculations are needed regarding demand for one period, ordering costs and storage costs. The number of requests has been calculated on ABC analysis.

a. Ordering Costs

Ordering costs include quota fees, administration and shipping costs.

1. Quota Fee

Based on interviews, the average time required for each order is 3-5 minutes/order. The Telkonsel quota rate is IDR 120.00 per minute (PT. Telkom Indonesia). So the cost for 5 minutes is IDR 600.00/order.

2. Administration/ ATK costs

ATK used by PT. Ciruas Food partners are:

ATK costs for ordering PPE every month

No	Goods	Lots	Price (Rp)	Amount (Rp)
1	HVS Paper	2 sheets	250.00	500.00
2	Fountain pen	1 piece	5,000.00	5,000.00
3	Shipping cost	1 time	15,000.00	15,000.00
The amount of costs				20,500.00

Based on the calculation results above, administration/ ATK costs for ordering personal protective equipment at PT. Ciruas Food's partners for the month are Rp. 20,500.00/order. so the ordering cost in one year is IDR 246,000.00.

So the total cost of one order personal protective equipment :
 =Quota Fee + Administration Fee
 =Rp. 600.00 +Rp. 20,500.00
 =Rp. 21,100.00

Total Cost Per Order at PT. Ciruas Food Partners

No	Order Fees	Order Fee (Rp)
1	Quota Fee	600.00
2	Administrative costs	20,500.00
Total Cost Per Order		21,100.00

Table of EOQ Calculation Results

No	Name	Total Usage	Order Fees (Rp)	Storage Fees (Rp)	EOQ	Purchase
1	Gloves Latex	814	21,100.00	875.00	198	4
2	Hairnets	218	21,100.00	1,750.00	73	3
3	Plastic Apron	815	21,100.00	420.00	287	3
4	Face mask	841	21,100.00	350.00	319	3
5	Cloth Aprons	5	21,100.00	21,000.00	10	1
6	Gloves	752	21,100.00	70.00	673	1

Table of Safety Stock and ROP Calculation Results

No	Name	Total Usage	Average Daily Usage	Lead time	Service Level (95%)	Safety Stock	ROP
1	Latex Gloves	814	3	3	1.65	15	24
2	Hairnets	218	1	3	1.65	5	8
3	Plastic Apron	815	3	3	1.65	15	24
4	Face mask	841	3	3	1.65	15	24
5	Cloth Aprons	5	1	3	1.65	5	8
6	Plastic gloves	752	2	3	1.65	10	16

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were obtained:

Based on the results of the analysis of the inventory of personal protective equipment at PT. Mitra Ciruas Food uses the ABC (always Better Control) method, there are 2 types of personal protective equipment items that fall into classification A, namely latex gloves and hair nets with a percentage of 57,935% of the total inventory of personal protective equipment with a total value of Rp1,562,500.00. Personal protective equipment included in group B is plastic aprons with a percentage of 18,131% of the total inventory of personal protective equipment with a total value of Rp.489,000.00. Meanwhile, personal protective equipment included in group C is masks, cloth aprons and plastic gloves with a percentage of 23,934% of the total inventory of personal protective equipment with total value, namely Rp.645,500.00. Based on the results of calculations using the Economic Order Quantity method, the number of economic orders for group A, namely latex gloves, is 198 pcs for one order, while the frequency of ordering latex gloves is 4 times and reordering when the supply of latex gloves has reached 24 items. . And tohair netis 73 pcs for one order while the order frequencyhair netis 3 times as well as reordering when stock is availablehair nethas reached 8 items.The number of economic orders for group B, namely plastic aprons, is 287 pcs for one order, while the frequency of ordering plastic aprons is 3 times and reordering when the supply of plastic aprons has reached 24 items. The number of economic orders for group C, namely masks, is 319 pcs for one order, while the frequency of ordering masks is 3 times and reordering when the supply of masks has reached 24 items. The number of orders for cloth aprons is 10 pcs for one order, while the frequency of ordering cloth aprons is 1 time and to order again when the supply of cloth aprons has reached 8 items. And finally, the number of orders for plastic gloves is 752 pcs for one order, while the frequency of ordering plastic gloves is 1 time and reordering when the supply of plastic gloves has reached 16 items.

SUGGESTION

After carrying out calculations and analysis regarding inventory control at PT. Ciruas Food Partners, suggestions that can be given are:

1. PT. Ciruas Food Partners needs to apply the ABC analysis method to personal protective equipment included in group A, because this group has a fairly high percentage.
2. In the process of supplying personal protective equipment PT. Ciruas Food Partners can use the results of EOQ calculations to obtain optimal order quantities to reduce costs incurred in terms of storing personal protective equipment.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, SR, Citraningtyas, G., & Mansauda, KLR (2021). "Controlling Drug Supplies Using Economic Order Quantity (EOQ) and Reorder Point (ROP) Methods at Pharmacy X, Wenang District". *Pelamonia Pharmaceutical Journal* Vol.(3). No. 10927-932.
- Agarwal, S. (2014). "Economic Order Quantity Model" *VSRD International Journal of Mechanical, Civil, Automobile and Production Engineering*, Vol. 4. No. (12). 233-236.
- Andira, Olivia S. (2016). "Analysis of Wheat Flour Raw Material Supplies Using the EOQ (Economic Order Quantity) Method on Roti Puncak Makassar". *Journal of Business Economics*. Vol.(21) No.(3): 1-8
- Anoraga, Panji. (2009). *Business management*. Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta.
- Dampung, VM (2021). "Pharmaceutical Preparation Planning Profile Using the ABC Method at the Pare-Pare City Health Service". *Journal Pharmacy Of Pelamonia*. Vol.(1).No.1: 25-28.
- Gaspersz, V. (2006). *Dramatic Cost and Waste Reduction Strategy Using the Lean-Sigma Approach*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Handoko, TH (2000). *Basics of Production and Operations Management*. Yogyakarta: BPFE.
- Heizer, J., & Render, B. (2010). *Operation management*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat
- Indrajit, RE and Pranoto RD (2003). *Inventory Management*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Widiasarana Indonesia.
- Mahatmyo, A. (2014). *Accounting Information Systems An Introduction*. Yogyakarta: Deepublish.
- Mardiyanto, H. (2009). *Digest of Financial Management*, Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Widiyasarana Indonesia (GRASINDO).
- Nasution, AH and Prasetyawan, YP (1999) *Production Planning and Control, (Revised Edition)*, Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu

- Nugraha, SW, & Wijaya, AR (2015). "Determination of Safety Stock, Reorder Point, and Order Quantity of Production Machine Parts Based on Uncertainty in Demand and Lead Time in Manufacturing Companies." Thesis. Yogyakarta: Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Industrial Engineering, Gadjah Mada University Yogyakarta. 91-98
- Pitoyo, J., & Wendanto, W. (2017). "UD Logam Jaya Klaten Inventory Management System". STMIK AUB Scientific Journal. Vol. 23, No (1). 8-17.
- Rangkuti., F. (2004). Inventory management applications in the business field. Jakarta: Erlangga
- Be patient, boy. S. (2009). Handbook for Hospital Management Students. Jakarta: Sagung Seto
- Seto, S. (2012). Pharmacy Management. Surabaya: Airlangga University Press.
- Sukhia, K. N., Khan, A. A., & Bano, M. (2014). "Introducing Economic Order Quantity Model For Inventory Control In Web Based Point Of Sale Applications And Comparative Analysis Of Techniques For Demand Forecasting In Inventory Management". International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 107. No.(19): 17385-18856.
- Sumayang. L. (2003). Basics of Production and Operations Management. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Winasari, A. (2015). "An overview of the causes of empty stock of patented medicines and efforts to control them in the medical warehouse of the Bekasi City Regional Hospital Pharmacy Installation in the first quarter" Thesis. Jakarta: Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Syarif Hidayatullah State Islamic University Jakarta Vol. 57. 1999-2014